

Shift2Maas

D5.1 Project logo & website

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Consortium of Partners

UNION INTERNATIONALE DES TRANSPORTS PUBLICS	Belgium
AETHON SYMVOULI MICHANIKI MONOPROSOPI IKE	Greece
CEFRIEL	Italy
OLTIS GROUP	Czech Republic
UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	United Kingdom
COMPANHIA CARRIS DE FERRO DE LISBOA	Portugal
EMPRESA MALAGUEÑA DE TRANSPORTES SAM	Spain
EMEL - EMPRESA PUBLICA MUNICIPAL DE ESTACIONAMENTO DE LISBOA	Portugal
VIA VERDE PORTUGAL-GESTAO DE SISTEMAS ELECTRONICOS DE COBRANCA	Portugal
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D5.1 Project logo &
website

Contract No. 826252

1 Executive summary

This document describes the objectives, structure, and look and feel of the Shift2MaaS logo and the Shift2MaaS website. Both the logo and website are essential tools within the Shift2MaaS project to reach project objectives concerning communication, including strengthening the project's identity, raising awareness and dissemination project developments to key stakeholders and external actors, and ensuring maximal exploitation of project results.

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2 Abbreviations and acronyms

EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
ITD	Integrated Technical Demonstrator
MAAS	Mobility as a Service
OC	Open Call
S2R	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
WP	Work Package

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3 Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D5.1 “Project logo & website” in the framework of the ITD4.7, WP5, task 5.1 of Shift2MaaS project (S2R-OC-IP4-02-2018).

4 Objectives/aim

The objectives of the Shift2MaaS communication activities are to raise awareness and disseminate project developments to key stakeholders and external actors, to ensure maximal exploitation of project results, to organise key project events, and finally to implement and update an appropriate online presence (website, social media). The Shift2MaaS logo and website are two tools developed to reach these objectives.

The project logo and an accompanying visual identity (colour scheme, fonts) have been developed to establish a strong project identity. A strong identity evokes recognition among stakeholders, ensures consistency in communication activities, and positions the Shift2MaaS project as a strong brand. The project logo will be used in many different ways throughout the project: it will be visible on the project website, on the project leaflet, in presentation templates, and on all other forms of communication material developed by the Shift2MaaS project.

The Shift2MaaS website is a communication tool for the consortium partners, relevant stakeholders, and the general public. Together with events, it will be one of the project's main gateways to reach target groups outside the consortium. The Shift2MaaS website will be regularly updated in order to provide an up to date picture of the project, report the latest developments and announce upcoming events. All of the website's content will be created in a way that is understandable and attractive to everyone accessing it, hereby ensuring reaching as many people as possible. Alongside being a platform for the general platform, the website also serves as a gateway to a 'private area', where everyone with access (mainly consortium members) can share documents in a secure environment.

5 Project logo

5.1 Logo

The Shift2MaaS logo was developed by a graphic designer after a dedicated briefing about the project. The logo was launched in January 2019 to be included in all communication materials for the project kick-off meeting, which took place on 10 January 2019.

Figure 1: the Shift2MaaS logo

In accordance with the project partners and following advice from the graphic designer, an innovative colour scheme has been chosen for the project, deviating from the more traditional combination of colours that are often used for projects, such as green and blue. This has been done to embody the innovative nature of the project.

The design of the logo has been chosen to reflect the main topic of the project, namely MaaS. The circle in the logo depicts a route, with the dots on the circle resembling different modes or locations, depending on interpretation. The logo has a modern look and feel, which has been chosen to follow the innovative character of the project.

5.2 Templates

To ensure consistent use of the Shift2MaaS logo and colours, various templates have been developed: a PowerPoint template, a deliverable template, a meeting minutes template, and a meeting agenda template. All consortium partners were encouraged to make use of these templates when presenting the Shift2MaaS project in internal or external meetings.

6 Project website

6.1 General

The Shift2MaaS website can be accessed via <http://shift2maas.eu/>. It was launched on 4 April 2019. The website is composed of seven different sections:

- Home
- Project
- Demonstration sites
- Partners
- Results & Publications
- News & Events
- Contact us

Each of these pages is divided into various subpages, which all elaborate a different element of the Shift2MaaS project.

Users of the website can access the private area (Cooperation Tool) via a header in the menu. Alongside a link to the private area, the header also includes a referral to the Shift2MaaS Twitter account, a button to contact the project directly via email (info@shift2maas.eu), and a link to the Shift2Rail website.

The footer displays the project logo, the EU flag and grant agreement number, and the full menu of the website. It also includes a link to the Shift2MaaS privacy policy.

On all pages of the website, users have the opportunity to log in to their Shift2MaaS account, after which they will have access to specific documents on the website. Registering for such an account is possible on the homepage only.

The website will be available up to five years after the project ends (in January 2021). This means that the website will also serve as a depository and a reference point for project related information and deliverables after the end of Shift2MaaS, supporting in this way the dissemination and exploitation strategies of the project.

6.2 Section 'Homepage'

The Homepage¹ section enables visitors to read what the project is about, in a brief instant. It includes a banner with five rotating pictures, which all include a brief sentence explaining the core of the project. The links on the banners lead the visitor directly to other pages and subpages. The homepage also includes a brief summary of the project. People who want to read more are referred to the 'Vision and Mission' subpage, which falls under the 'Project' page. The homepage also includes an overview of the latest news and events. Finally, users have the opportunity to register to the Shift2MaaS newsletter on the homepage. When doing this, they are asked to accept the GDPR policy and authorise the handling of their personal data.

¹ <http://www.shift2maas.eu/>

Figure 2: the Shift2MaaS website homepage

6.3 Section 'Project'

The five subpages under the 'Project' tab² (Vision and mission; At a glance; Objectives; Approach; Context) are the most text-heavy parts of the website. The 'At a glance' subpage has been added to this part of the website to provide a very brief overview of the project. Finally, the 'Context' subpage explains the role of Shift2MaaS within the Shift2Rail programme and dives deeper into the structure and objectives IP4.

OBJECTIVES

The main goal of Shift2MaaS is to support the uptake the **IP4 technology** and to overcome the barriers for the adoption of new and integrated Mobility as a Service (MaaS) platforms to enable seamless passenger experience.

To achieve this, the Shift2MaaS project has the following objectives:

- 1 Design the demonstrations for Shift2Rail IP4 technologies deployment in real environments.
- 2 Provide support to and build bridges with the related Shift2Rail COHESIVE project.
- 3 Guarantee a technical coordination interface with other Shift2Rail IP4 projects (in particular COHESIVE, CONNECTIVE and future related projects), to address interoperability between systems involved in the demonstrations.
- 4 Assess the impact of Shift2Rail IP4 technologies on the selected demonstration sites by designing an evaluation framework.
- 5 Analyse the impact of IP4 technologies on business models and on the behaviour of passengers.

Figure 3: the Shift2MaaS 'Objectives' section

² <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=STANDARD&IdPage=316f9751-07f0-4c50-8efc-aff76adf7e8>

6.4 Section ‘Demonstration sites’

Consisting of the subpages ‘Lisbon’, ‘Malaga’, and ‘Central-East Corridor’, the ‘Demonstration Sites’ section³ elaborates on the pilots within the Shift2MaaS project. Because the pilots will take their final form throughout the project, the information on these pages will be adapted later.

LISBON

Lisbon Metropolitan Area is the biggest agglomeration in Portugal, with a population of about 2.8 million people, in which residences and activities are highly centered around the city of Lisbon. Over recent decades private transport, mostly passenger cars, have become the most popular transport mode in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. With a motorisation rate of 433 passenger cars per thousand inhabitants and a modal share of private vehicles of over 50% (and public transport below 30%), there is now a strong political commitment to reverse these numbers and promote public transport. An important element of the strategy to address this challenge is the modernisation of public transport and its integration in digital transport networks.

Figure 4: the Shift2MaaS ‘Lisbon’ section

6.5 Section ‘Partners’

On the ‘Partners’ section⁴, all logos of the consortium partners within the Shift2MaaS project are displayed, including a link to their websites.

³ <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=STANDARD&IdPage=663bc042-da0a-4d5e-b73c-9ef3775d3cea>

⁴ <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=PARTNERS&IdPage=9dfdc8a2-5d58-4487-a34f-10e1f8b3d0be>

OTHER PARTNERS

Figure 5: the Shift2MaaS 'Partners' section

6.6 Section 'Results & Publications'

Consisting of 'Deliverables' and 'Other publications', the 'Results & Publications' section⁵ will serve as the library of the website. All public deliverables will be uploaded to this section, as well as project publications such as newsletters, the leaflet, and other interesting content.

6.7 Section 'News & Events'

The 'News & Events'⁶ section will see the posting of all news items about the Shift2MaaS project: this can be an event the project was presented at, the announcement of a new deliverable, or any interesting industry news. Furthermore, all external events that the Shift2MaaS consortium will attend, will be posted in this section.

NEWS

10 JANUARY 2019

SHIFT2MAAS PROJECT KICKS OFF IN BRUSSELS

On 10 January 2019, the Shift2MaaS kick-off meeting took place at the Crowne Plaza Hotel in Brussels. The event was held jointly with the kick-off meeting of SPRINT, a different ...

[MORE DETAILS](#)

Figure 6: a news item on the Shift2MaaS website

⁵ <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=DELIVERABLES&IdPage=e9811fda-f7db-4ee3-845f-db86fa80443a>

⁶ <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=NEWS&IdPage=9ceb0cfe-4a65-4c76-85f9-2f6343b2cf0a>

6.8 Section 'Contact us'

The contact section⁷ offers the possibility to send a message to the project consortium and contains the direct contact of the Shift2MaaS Coordinator (represented by Project Manager Ms Daria Kuzmina), as well as the general project email address.

Figure 7: the Shift2MaaS 'Contact' section

⁷ <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Contacts.aspx?CAT=CONTACTS&IdPage=46864768-a7cc-4e0f-9213-cce0ff969f77>

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7 Conclusions

By developing a logo and project website early in the project, two essential steps towards a coherent and consistent project identity have been made. By consistently using the Shift2MaaS logo and visual identity, the project will gain recognition among relevant stakeholders and become a solid brand. Furthermore, by developing the Shift2MaaS website and regularly updating it with news, events, articles, deliverables and other communication materials, constant interaction with relevant stakeholders will be ensured. This communication tool, alongside the Shift2MaaS Twitter account and the future e-newsletter, will build a relationship with the Shift2MaaS target groups and increase engagement among them. The fact that the website will be available up to five years after the project has been completed, means that the Shift2MaaS project aims to be a reference point for project related questions for a longer time, supporting in this way the exploitation and dissemination strategies of the project.

8 References

1. Shift2MaaS project. "Homepage". Accessed 23/04/2019. <http://www.shift2maas.eu/>
2. Shift2MaaS project. "Project". Accessed 23/04/2019. <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=STANDARD&IdPage=316f9751-07f0-4c50-8efc-aff76adf7e8>
3. Shift2MaaS project. "Demonstration sites". Accessed 23/04/2019. <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=STANDARD&IdPage=663bc042-da0a-4dbe-b73c-9ef3775d3cea>
4. Shift2MaaS project. "Partners". Accessed 23/04/2019. <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=PARTNERS&IdPage=9dfdc8a2-5d58-4487-a34f-10e1f8b3d0be>
5. Shift2MaaS project. "Results & Publications". Accessed 23/04/2019. <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=DELIVERABLES&IdPage=e9811fda-f7db-4ee3-845f-db86fa80443a>
6. Shift2MaaS project. "News & Events". Accessed 23/04/2019. <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Page.aspx?CAT=NEWS&IdPage=9ceb0cfe-4a65-4c76-85f9-2f6343b2cf0a>
7. Shift2MaaS project. "Contact us". Accessed 23/04/2019. <http://www.shift2maas.eu/Contacts.aspx?CAT=CONTACTS&IdPage=46864768-a7cc-4e0f-9213-cce0ff969f77>